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Pharmacognosy: An important sub-discipline of pharmacy

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Abstract:

Pharmacognosy might be thought of as the original field from which pharmacy has grown. This study provides a definition of pharmacognosy while considering recent advancements, discussions on its justifiability in the training system at pharmaceutical faculties, and the history of new drug development influenced by pharmacognosy. The current state of the field of pharmacognosy, or more specifically, its components (biology, chemistry, production, and technology), is defined in the article along with their linkages. It demonstrates the obvious legitimacy of using natural medicines in therapy and shows that it doesn't matter how a new drug was made—synthetically or by isolating it from a natural source. The overview adheres to the fundamental principles of pharmacognosy, particularly its methodology (use of quicker and more accurate Phyto-analytical procedures, reverse pharmacology, and reverse pharmacognosy, in silico approaches). The evaluation of ethnopharmacological sources, the assessment of nutraceuticals, and the pharmacognosy of marine species are the three principal issues that face pharmacognosy in the twenty-first century and have the potential to greatly advance it.

Keywords:

Pharmacognosy, Pharmacy, Science, Natural Substances, Herbal Medicine.

1. Introduction:

The term "pharmacognosy," which comes from the Greek words "pharmakon" (drug) and "gnosis" (knowledge), refers to the study of crude drugs of plant and animal origin (in the form of tinctures, teas, poultices, powders, and other herbal formulations). It also includes authentication and quality control of such drugs, which are based on macroscopic and microscopic analyses of crude drugs. Schmidt, an Austrian physician, coined the word "pharmacognosy" in 1811; Seydler followed suit with his publication of "Analecta Pharmacognostica" in 1815.

Since its inception about 200 years ago, pharmacognosy has developed over time, and today it can be characterized as the science of biogenic or naturally derived drugs, pharmaceuticals, and poisons. It also incorporates a number of contemporary analytical techniques to authenticate and control the quality of raw drugs as well as purified active extracts, fractions, and components, and even therapeutic foods. The field of pharmacognosy has evolved along with the usage of therapeutics derived from medicinal plants, moving from the preparation of crude medications to the isolation, identification, and evaluation of the bioactivity of active chemicals in drug development.

The American Society of Pharmacognosy defines Pharmacognosy as "the study of the physical, chemical, biochemical and biological properties of drugs, drug substances, or potential drugs or drug substances of natural origin as well as the search for new drugs from natural sources." Modern Pharmacognosy involves the broad study of natural products from various sources including plants, bacteria, fungi, and marine organisms.

The goal of pharmacognosy, a specialty area of pharmacy that focuses on natural products, is to identify the sources of natural drugs and the products of their metabolism that can be used for treatment, disease prevention, and diagnostic purposes in human and veterinary medicine. It also aims to explain the biosynthesis of biologically active substances as well as the possibilities and techniques for isolating, identifying, and technologically modifying. It must discuss recombinant methods to produce pharmaceuticals from genetically modified organisms as well as the fundamentals of structure determination. It must also hint at the possibility of partial synthetic modifications leading to the demand for either modification or adjustment of action.

2. History of Pharmacognosy:

The pharmaceutical sciences' oldest subfield is pharmacognosy. Plants have been used as medicines since the Stone Age. The people of that period found the medications they need for their therapeutic usage and were able to distinguish between hazardous and beneficial plants by simple observation and experimentation. Folk medicine developed as a result of learning about illicit substances. Primitive man discovered which plants were harmful and which were excellent for eating very gradually. Additionally, they discovered that some plants (spices or condiments) could be utilized to make extracts that might be employed as arrow or spear poison as well as preserve meat and mask undesirable flavours. The discovery of plants' therapeutic qualities was credited to the gods and it was believed that medicinal plants and herbs were the homes of good spirits or deities while poisonous plants were the homes of evil spirits. Since the beginning of human history, vegetable drug collectors have been documented and many medications that are still in use today had their start in this manner. It is frequently discovered that plants with a reputation for being medicinal are those that are most deserving of in-depth scientific research, indicating that medicinal development is still at this stage among certain primitive people today.

The following are the contributions of each period:

2.1. Ancient Egyptian Period:

The Ancient Egyptians were adept in using pharmaceuticals to treat illness around 3000 B.C. Priest doctor and pharmacist "son" who made prescriptions and produced medications worked to treat the ill. In Egyptian tombs, the earliest written prescriptions were discovered. The hieratic papyri are those. E. Smith discovered the surgical papyrus, which is considered to be the most priceless papyrus. It is a copy of an ancient manuscript from 2980 to 2700 B.C. The other two papyri are the gynaecologic papyrus of Kahun and Gurob and the Ebers papyrus, which dates back 3500 years and is currently on display at the University of Leipzig. They do, however, comprise 400 basic ingredients that were likely included in the ancient Egyptians' "Egyptian pharmacopeia." The first category of these elements consists of items that are derived from animals, such as blood, meat, horn, milk, eggs, honey, wine, and excrement. Materials of vegetative origin, such as acacia, aloes, gum, myrrh, pomegranate, colocynth, linseed, coriander, cumin, anise, castor, etc., are included in the second group. The whole vegetative kingdom was utilized, including the roots, rhizomes, flowers, leaves, fruits, seeds, oils, and ashes.

2.2. The Mesopotamian Therapy:

The interpretations of the tables inscribed in cuneiform writing provide information on Babylonian medicine. The majority of the medications utilized were made from plants. A garden of therapeutic plants, including apples, pomegranates, cucumbers, oranges, garlic, onions, saffron, fennel, thyme, coriander, roses, laurel, and liquorice, was created by the Babylonian monarch Marduk (772 B.C.). The administration of the medications in the form of a decoction, which is often delivered before daybreak because the decoctions were prepared by night, was the second significant observation. Typically, the medications were dissolved in honey, water, oil, or wine. The Mesopotamian formulas have 250 plant-based ingredients and 180 animal-based ingredients. The ancient Egyptians were aware of several of these medications.

2.3. Old Indian Medicine:

Old Indian medicine's main goal was to extend people's lives, which is why it was important to learn the secrets of plant-based medications. So, the frightened medicinal herbs were included in the "Rig Veda" and Ayurveda (Acoko 2000 B.C.). Fresh plants were thought to be the most effective, and they had to be dug out of rich soil, well cleaned with pure water, exposed to the sun for a while, then shielded in the shadow, always facing north. They divided medications into two groups: purgatives, which include cathartics, emetics, and these substances that increase nasal flow, and tranquilizers. As basis for oral medications, they employed butter, honey, sugar, and sesame oil. The most celebrated Indian drugs are; Sandal wood, Clove, Pepper, Cardamom, Caraway, Ginger, Castor oil, Sesame oil, Aloes, Galangal and cane sugar.

2.4. Chinese Medicine:

Aside from the well-known acupuncture, Chinese medicine is also known for its herbal remedies. There were a staggering number of medicinal herbs and medications with animal origins in the Pen Ts'ao Kang Moa, which was written around 1000 B.C. but only published in 1597. The Chinese believed that there should be a natural remedy available for every sickness. As a result, every ailment has several recipes in their book. Ginseng is one of the plants revered for its mystical ability to improve health; other medicines, such as rhubarb, star anise, pomegranate, and aconite, were also widely used. The Pen Ts'ao Kang Moa, which has 8160 formulations made from 1871 raw components primarily of vegetable origin, might be seen as

a pharmacopeia. Decoctions, powders, tablets, poultices, suppositories, and ointments were among the forms of medication employed.

2.5. The Greek and Roman Period:

Medication was used to treat several ailments. Pythagoras used medicines like mustard about 580 B.C. Hippocrates (466 B.C.) wrote the Corpus Hipocraticum and was knowledgeable about a number of drugs. Theophrastus, an Aristotelian student who lived in 370 B.C., named over 500 plants, and ergot was one of them. The number of medications that were known at the period increased as a result of Alexander the Great's invasion (335-325 B.C.). The Roman Empire succeeded the Greek Empire, and Dioscorides, a Greek by origin, travelled to Egypt and other Mediterranean Sea-bordering nations where he got familiar with a wide range of plants and medications. He was the first to describe pharmaceuticals, and his book "Greek Herbal of Dioscorides" contained descriptions of medications derived from both animals and minerals as well as at least 5000 different medicinal plants. He is regarded as the earliest known pharmacist. Galen (134-299 A.D.) was a physician and to him is ascribed the use of "Galenical preparations".

2.6. The Islamic Contribution:

The lengthy period of the dark ages began in Europe when the Roman Empire fell. The Greek and Roman medical literature was translated into Arabic by the Islamic culture, who also added their own commentary and original insights. This is how they picked up the medical torch and kept it burning. The oldest mention of chemistry may be found in Islamic books; the word "chemistry" itself, like the English "alcohol" and "alkali," is derived from the Arabic word "kemia." The older medical expertise was brought back to Europe via Islamic literature. To the plants and medicines that the Greeks and Romans already knew, the Arabs contributed a large number of new ones. Back then, pharmacy had gained the height of its fame and had evolved into a separate medical specialty. It's important to note that Baghdad, the hub of trade at the time, was the location of the first dispensary. The dispensary was called "Sandalia" and was constructed from sandal wood. Ibn Sina (980–1037 AD) stood out among Islamic authors. His "Canon" of medicine has been referred to be the most renowned medical literature ever published and has dominated medical schools in Europe and Asia for five centuries, up to the fifteenth century.

Ibn Al-Baitar, who ranks alongside Dioscorides in this regard, was the greatest Arabian pharmacognocist and botanist. His book "Jame-ul-Muffradat" describes 2000 different medications. Dawood El-Antaki, Shaikh. The author of "Tazkarat Uli Al-Albab," now known as "Tazkarat Dawood Antaki," wrote a book in the year 1008 A.D. that lists hundreds of plants in addition to medicines with animal and mineral origins.

2.7. Folklore Medicine:

The understanding of the preventative and therapeutic effects of unrefined substances that has been accumulated over millennia has contributed to the development of folk medicine. These knowledge was collected from the numerous sources like verbally through conversations with witches, hunters, tribal wardens, herbalists, attars, and Bedouins and were recorded in ancient Egyptian papyri, cuneiforms scripts of Hamorabi, Rigveda & Ayrvedas of Vedic Sanskrit of India, Pen Ts'ao Kang Moa of Chinam Corpus Hippocraticum, Greek herbal of Dioscorides, El Kanon Fil Tib of Aircena, Sharh Asmaa El Okar of El Kortobi, Tazkarat Oli Al Albab of El Antaki and Mofradat Al Adwiah Wal Agzia of Ibn El Bitar.

2.8. Modern Pharmacognosy:

The first books with descriptions of medicines that are now known as "Materia Medica" were "Herbals," such as "Hortus Sanitatis," which translates to "garden of health" in Latin and was published in Mainz in 1491. It contained things of mineral, animal, and vegetable origin that were grouped alphabetically.

Modern analytic chemistry methods and techniques, such as paper, thin layer, gas chromatography, and spectrophotometry, were simultaneously applied to the fields of organic chemistry, biochemistry, pharmacology, and biosynthesis to develop modern pharmacognosy later, between the years 1934 and 1960. Purified chemicals from the plants were examined for pharmacologically potent elements, and their structures and internal organization were defined. The following four occurrences were the key causes of the development:

- Isolation of penicillin in 1928 by William Fleming and large-scale production in 1941 by Florey and Chain.
- Isolation of reserpine from rauwolfia roots and con-firming its hypotensive and tranquilizing properties.

- Isolation of vinca alkaloids, especially vincristine and vinblastine. Vincristine was found useful in the treatment of leukaemia. These alkaloids also have anticancer properties.
- Steroid hormones like progesterone were isolated by partial synthesis from diosgenin and other steroid saponins by Marker's method. Cortisone and hydro-cortisone are obtained from progesterone by chemical and microbial reaction.

This period can also be termed antibiotic age, as besides penicillin, active antibiotics like streptomycin, chloramphenicol, tetracycline and several hundred antibiotics have been isolated and studied extensively.

3. Areas affecting Pharmacognosy:

It is vital to identify the fields that pharmacognosy encompasses, either fully or partially, in order to evaluate its current viability as an academic (educational) and practical field:

3.1. Biological disciplines:

- Pharmacognosy sensu stricto (basic verification methods, macroscopy, microscopy).
- Pharmacobotany (ethnobotany, physiology, and biochemistry of secondary metabolites).
- Genetics (creation of chemical varieties by gene recombination for field production).
- Biotechnology (microbiology, production of substances, by various cell types in vitro, usage of recombinant DNA technologies, enzymes fixed to a carrier).
- Pharmacology and toxicology of natural substances (basic characteristics of biological effect, primary toxicity of newly isolated compounds, detection of undesirable impurities).

3.2. Chemical disciplines:

- Isolation phytochemistry (optimal procedure for obtaining active substances).
- Analytical phytochemistry (qualitative and quantitative analytical chemistry of natural compounds).
- Preparative organic chemistry (preparation of derivatives and structure modification of isolated compounds).

- Structural analysis methods.

❖ **Production of raw materials:**

- Production of biogenic material (agrotechnics, field production).
- Technology of natural drugs (processing of biogenic raw materials, substances isolation on an industrial scale).

3.3. Technical disciplines:

- Computer methods (chemical docking).
- Cataloguing and classification of natural raw materials.

It is impossible to pick out any one of these disciplines because the entirety of pharmacognosy is made up of all of them, the majority of which are preliminary. This is amply supported by data from the literature on the subject of pharmacognosy, including emerging fields like forensic, molecular, and Eco pharmacognosy; this is a response to the ongoing process of unambiguous verification of pharmaceuticals based on their genetic profile (DNA) and subsequently the metabolome. It also provides computer-aided methods for monitoring the metabolome of natural sources as well as the use of molecular tools to assess the quality of biogenic material. Traditional pharmacognostical techniques are continuously being improved, and they produce good results when used correctly.

4. Significance of Pharmacognosy:

- It is important for the creation of novel medications.
- It serves as a bridge between the conventional and modern medical systems.
- In conjunction with the contemporary medical system, it offers safe and efficient medications.
- It is more successful at treating patients today since it is knowledgeable about the safe use of herbal medications, including their adverse effects, toxicity, drug interactions, etc.
- It serves as a bridge between medicinal chemistry and pharmacology.
- Because of pharmacognosy, new plant drugs are finding their way into medicines as purified phytochemicals.

4.1. Justification of Natural Substances in the Present Scenario:

The examination of the number of medications containing these ingredients and medications developed from natural formulae that are listed in the WHO's List of Basic Medicinal Products shows the significance of natural products in therapy. The 13th revision covers about 210 small-molecule medicines and close to 300 other compounds that are thought to be fundamental to medical practice. These include over 70 synthetic medications based on pharmaceuticals comprising natural chemicals or synthetically modified natural structures, as well as 44 unmodified natural items, 25 semi-synthetic derivatives of natural goods, and 25 semi-synthetic derivatives of natural products. The concept of the origin of natural compounds in the review adheres to the convention set out by Newman, Crag, and Snader, taking into account the evolution of such substances over time as well as the antecedents of the pertinent drug prototypes. Jones et al. gives a thorough picture of the region at the turn of the century. As about half of the new chemical entities entering the new medicine approval process are either natural products or related compounds, these authors believe that medicines derived from natural sources make up about half of prescription medicines and are likely to do so in the future. Natural goods' significance in modern medicine is not merely a holdover from the common history of medicine and plant-based medications. Natural compounds are a great source for the development of novel medications. Additionally, biogenic-based products play a significant role in contemporary medicine and pharmacy, and it is crucial for natural medicines to continue to be researched by pharmacognosists and other experts in natural products in order to understand their active principles and mechanisms of action.

4.2. 21st Century Pharmacognosy:

It must be acknowledged that pharmacognosy continues to hold a lot of public attention at this time. Compared to earlier decades, the usage of biogenic resources has increased in the last ten years. More individuals simultaneously have faith in pharmaceuticals. The range of these items is expanding in the global pharmacy, and pharmacy students are becoming more interested in this field. The scientific community is becoming more interested in phytopharmaceuticals, which are still an important element of several nations' pharmaceutical schools' curricula. There is growing funding opportunity and scientific interest in the components of natural medicines and nutraceuticals, but there is also growing competition from those working in industries outside of academic pharmaceutical institutions who see this area as a mainstay and are looking to capitalize on it. In the process of finding new medicines, pharmacognosists' excellent

expertise may be quite helpful. With the expansion of scientific fields and their growth, the resolution of new projects that are established in the future might be thought of as more difficult than in the 20th century. To guarantee that pharmacognosy as a field does not perish, it is hoped that as pharmacognosy research grows more specialized, it will find a strong and cohesive representation at national and international events. With new development trends like combinatorial synthesis, genomics, and proteomics at the forefront, work on the development of pharmacognosy should engage individuals with the broadest professional backgrounds feasible. Natural substance researchers (and academics) will need to be more adaptable than before, but because of new techniques and resources accessible, the advantages will be much higher than before in terms of their own scientific curiosity and for society. Pharmacognosy may, without a doubt, anticipate the future with enormous excitement.

It was obvious by the end of the 20th century that pharmacists who had a broad education, were creative in drug research, and have improvisational abilities due to their academic training in all facets of pharmacy were going to play a key role in pharmacognosy.

Pharmacognosy currently faces three new challenges that have not been practically applied before:

- The first is the assessment of ethnic groups' traditional medicines, such as those from traditional Chinese medicine, traditional Indian medicine, traditional Japanese medicine, and traditional Mongolian medicine, which are used in pharmaceutical products and are based on cultural tradition rather than receptor theory.
- The examination of biogenic material (extracts and pure compounds) and preparations that lack the legally binding nature of drugs but are nutraceuticals, dietary supplements, or innovative foods provide the second problem. Despite being special meals for which no therapeutic justification is required, they are nonetheless significant in therapy and need to be evaluated. Nutraceuticals are frequently employed as a component of regulated therapy and, in some cases, even as the therapeutic agent itself in self-medication, which has a significant practical influence on pharmacies in addition to their significant commercial one. Although various procedures are in progress at the EU level, the problem is still complicated and needs to be handled through law. Political opinion cannot take the place of expert opinion, which must be founded on pharmacy-pharmacognosy. Even if they are foods, the issue of nutraceuticals needs to be treated in accordance with current understanding.

- The pharmacognosy of aquatic creatures poses the third difficulty. The first reference of their usage was made 50 years ago, and their deeper development occurred around 40 years ago (for example, in Sweden). Many articles demonstrate the depth of this field of pharmacognosy. To succeed in isolating macromolecular compounds with unexpected effects, pharmacist-pharmacologists must be properly equipped to employ current methodologies as part of their academic training. The main focus of pharmacognosy continues to be on small-molecule drugs, which are considerably simpler to work with.

Reverse pharmacognosy and reverse pharmacology are crucial components of contemporary pharmacognosy because they concentrate on discovering natural resources that include active molecules and targets for natural chemicals through virtual or actual screening. High-throughput screening (HTS), virtual screening, and knowledge databases comprising conventional plant applications are among the methods employed. Reverse pharmacognosy employs natural metabolites to identify possibly novel medicinal characteristics of natural material, in contrast to traditional pharmacognosy, which uses plants to identify new bioactive chemicals. The process of research may be accelerated and made more efficient by including reverse pharmacognosy and pharmacognosy into it.

Target-based drug discovery, also known as reverse pharmacology, is based on two steps: first, it is postulated that altering the activity of a particular protein target would have positive therapeutic effects. Studies in small-molecule chemical libraries are then employed to find substances that have a strong affinity for the target. The findings of this screening serve as a springboard for the identification of potential medication candidates. This technique has gained popularity for sequencing the human genome, making it possible to quickly create vast quantities of purified proteins. It is now the most used in the field of drug development.

4.3. Education and Pharmacognosy:

In nations with robust economies, pharmacognosy is becoming more and more common, and pharmacognostical research—for which erudite professionals are required—is gaining fresh impetus since it presents the chance to make considerable financial contributions to development. Natural chemicals and their derivatives have historically produced a number of therapeutically valuable medications. As a review study from the United Kingdom (1997) demonstrates, complications can arise once pharmacognosy does not have a comprehensive position in the educational system, particularly from the perspective of academic research. At

the time, only a few of the 16 pharmaceutical higher education institutions had significant expertise in pharmacognosy. The causes are numerous and in part stem from the absence of phytotherapy in the nation's traditional medicine. Herbal medications have been widely available in recent years, yet many pharmacists are unaware of the drugs they sell because of a widespread lack of pharmacognosy education. Further complicating matters is the rise in interest in Chinese and Indian herbal remedies due to the multicultural makeup of contemporary Britain. Pharmacists must work hard to address this education gap because pharmacognostical research is also conducted at nonpharmaceutical institutions.

In pharmaceutical universities, the master's and doctoral curricula both include pharmacognosy as a legitimate pharmaceutical specialty. There are several review studies that assess the trends in and development of pharmacognosy. Only two of the representative works in the profile are relevant to highlight, in our opinion. The first is the aforementioned letter by Alamgir, which discusses how current pharmacognosy has developed mostly in terms of classical characteristics. Despite significant successes, the traditional isolation and biological testing approach to the discovery of new drugs has its own limitations in a certain time-consuming nature. Jones et Al's opinions, which speak of new trends and prospects for pharmacognosy, must also be taken into consideration. In order to properly make natural substance research compatible with HTS, new techniques must be implemented because this problem may disadvantage approaches to the study of natural substances in the current environment. Different methods are suggested for these partially mentioned activities, including screening libraries of natural substances (molecular libraries), reevaluating the idea of "inactive compound," improving the isolation and clarification of substance structure, using contemporary spectroscopic techniques and biological tests, and developing chromatographic technologies (such as hyphenation techniques and contemporary extraction methods) as well as in silico methamphetamine testing.

Steinhoff, whose logical viewpoint ought to be acknowledged, made pertinent comments on the place of pharmacognosy in the future of academic education. It is undeniable that modernisation is required to keep up with advancements in science and technology, but it turns out that the fundamental understanding of classical pharmacognosy cannot be dropped from the curriculum for pharmacists. The academic training of pharmacists has traditionally included pharmacognosy. It used to be a traditional perspective on natural material (mainly plants) and cannot be disregarded in history, but in the last 20 years it has become important to conform to

current development trends. This knowledge is crucial for the practical activities of a pharmacist because it forms the basis of scientific phytotherapy and the use of products that have been fully recognized as medicines under European law (for instance, in accordance with European Directive 2004/24/EC, the Committee for Herbal Medicinal Products—HMPC—was established in 2004 and registration procedure for traditional herbal medicinal products). Regarding the fundamental abilities of aspiring pharmacists, their familiarity with medicinal plants, and their proficiency in the use of herbal medicines, there appears to be agreement on the need of pharmacognostical studies. According to the European Scientific Cooperative on Phytotherapy (ESCOP), all biogenic chemicals must be mentioned in relation to the fundamental academic competencies. The pharmacist might potentially benefit from academic training that exclusively addressed current scientific developments in the realm of chemical pharmaceuticals, but this training would limit the pharmacist's capacity to recognize medicinal plants and their constituent parts as well as their pharmacological effects and therapeutic efficacy. The only modern pharmacognosy that can succeed is one that is well-balanced, clearly defines its own role in the education of pharmacists, and also finds its place among other profile areas of the academic training of pharmacists, such as pharmacology, pharmaceutical chemistry, and technologies, which it can enhance.

4.4. Need for Students to Study Pharmacognosy:

Pharmacognosy is significant in the realm of pharmacy since it aids in the discovery of new medications to treat human disease. Natural medicines are typically challenging to produce in big amounts; hence research is required to create novel biologic medications. These compounds can undergo alterations during synthetic synthesis, including improved effectiveness, altered pharmacokinetics, and greater bioavailability. As certain anticancer drugs have shown, these modifications may transform a straightforward, ineffectual natural plant into a powerful pharmaceutical. Natural compounds can thus be used as ideal models for the development of new medications. The emergence of new wonder drugs that can be produced in a lab has led to a reduction in pharmacognosy's utilization, which was once recognized as a crucial component of drug discovery processes and pharmacy education.

Given its definition and course, pharmacognosy is one of the fundamental subjects that the pharmacy curriculum covers. People employ plants and plant extracts for self-medication. Since many therapies employ natural components, understanding the history is crucial. A pharmacist's job is to understand the illness and treat it with the best option available, thus they

should be knowledgeable about popular treatments and how they interact with other drugs, both manufactured and natural. Because plants are often the most significant source of cutting-edge drugs, understanding how to use herbs medicinally is essential. Pharmacy students should consequently be knowledgeable in order to carry out our responsibilities as authority on drugs and drug-related concerns. They should also be knowledgeable with plant-based medications, including its purpose, key active ingredients, possible drug interactions, and adverse effects. Thus, it is crucial to educate pharmacy students about pharmacognosy.

4.5. Career Prospective for M. Pharm Pharmacognosy Candidates:

There are many and varied career opportunities available to new M. Pharm in Pharmacognosy graduates worldwide. Additionally, having an M. Pharm in Pharmacognosy course boosts employment prospects. Jobs for M. Pharm in Pharmacognosy in India are based on knowledge, abilities, and work history. Graduates can get M. Pharm in Pharmacognosy jobs in a variety of industries in India. The M. Pharm in Pharmacognosy pay in India is also greater than it has ever been due to increased demand. The following positions in M. Pharm pharmacognosy are the most prevalent:

- Regulatory Manager.
- Drug Inspector.
- Lab Technician.
- Health Care Unit Manager.
- Analytical Chemist.
- Medical Transcriptionist.

A two-year postgraduate degree program that can help further a person's profession is offered through the M. Pharm in Pharmacognosy. A candidate's career is boosted by this course, making it possible for them to be given consideration for positions during the recruiting of professionals. As a result, the compensation for pharmacognosy graduates in India is constantly rising. For occupations requiring a master's degree in pharmacy sciences, recruiting occurs most frequently in the following fields:

- Hospitals.
- Herbal Industry.
- Medical and Research Laboratories.

- Pharmaceutical Industry.
- Government and Private Companies.
- Health clinics.

The average pay for pharmacognosy graduates in India is reportedly approximately INR 2.7 LPA, according to "Payscale." The amount of study, grades, and talents are what decide the occupations available after earning an M. Pharm in pharmacognosy. Following are some frequent positions for M. Pharm. in Pharmacognosy with typical salaries:

Table 1: Frequent positions for M. Pharm. in Pharmacognosy with typical salaries

Job Role	Average Annual Salary
School Teacher	INR 2.3 LPA
Analytical Chemist	INR 3.7LPA
Associate Research Scientist	INR 6.4 LPA
Biomedical Scientist	INR 3.9 LPA
Toxicologist	INR 7.8 LPA
Lab Technician	INR 2.38 LPA

For a long-term collaboration, many government hospitals, clinics, colleges, etc. accept M. Pharm in Pharmacognosy students. Professor, Quality Controller, Pharmacologist, and other positions in the Central Government are available for M. Pharm in Pharmacognosy. The average M. Pharm in Pharmacognosy remuneration for government positions is around INR 2.7 LPA according to "Payscale". Several government positions for M. Pharm. in Pharmacognosy are listed below:

Table 2: Government positions for M. Pharm. in Pharmacognosy

Job Role	Average Annual Salary
Government Teacher	INR 2 LPA
Quality Controller	INR 2.97 LPA

Pharmacologist	INR 5.12 LPA
Forensic Scientist	INR 5 LPA
Medical Transcriptionist	INR 2.1 LPA

The M. Pharm. in Pharmacognosy has a wide range of employment possibilities in the private sector. Private businesses, healthcare facilities, hospitals, and other industries where medical expertise and specialists are needed provide private employment opportunities. The M. Pharm in Pharmacognosy pay is around INR 2.7 LPA, according to “Payscale”. Jobs for M. Pharm in Pharmacognosy include the following:

Table. 3: Salary in private jobs for M. Pharm in Pharmacognosy

Job Roles	Average Annual Salary
Industrial Pharmacist	INR 3.80 LPA
Sales and Distribution Executive	INR 2.90 LPA
Hospital and Community Pharmacist	INR 2.90 LPA
Research Scientist	INR 6.6 LPA
Drug Inspector	INR 1.42 LPA
Regulatory Manager	INR 5.7 LPA

5. Conclusion:

Pharmacognosy has always been a transdisciplinary or interdisciplinary discipline, and as the field's focus has expanded, phytochemistry and phytochemical analysis have taken on significant roles. Through the selection and use of appropriate screening assays targeted toward physiologically relevant molecular targets, molecular biology has become crucial to the discovery of medicinal plant drugs. Modern pharmacognosy also incorporates all these pertinent new fields into a unique interdisciplinary science. From concentrating on the discovery of medications, including the isolation of active principles, and more recently, the examination of biological activity, the emphasis and focus of research in pharmacognosy have shifted substantially. Pharmacognosy now includes significant amounts of research into

ethnobotany, ethnomedicine, and ethnopharmacology. Pharmacognosy, still now, continues to play a crucial role in the discovery and development of novel medications and treatments. Additionally, it served as the foundation for the growth of the field of "pharmacy." It is regrettable that Pharmacognosy is no longer emphasized as a key subject in most current pharmacy courses, particularly in the West. One should not overlook the value of conventional medications made from plants only to satisfy the latest contemporary medicine hype. The need for modern pharmacists to be knowledgeable about conventional drugs has never been greater.

A multimodal strategy integrating botanical, computational, phytochemical, biological, and molecular approaches is now being used in drug development from therapeutic plants. It is clear that the development of novel and significant leads for drugs against a variety of pharmacological targets, such as cancer, HIV/AIDS, Alzheimer's, malaria, and pain, comes from the study of medicinal plants. Pharmacognosy has grown and changed throughout the years to adapt to the changing environment, and it is now capable of overcoming the obstacles facing drug discovery and development now and in the future. Therefore, it is impossible to overstate the significance of pharmacognosy in pharmacy. Pharmacognosy should be an intrinsic element of any worthwhile academic pharmacy programs across the world since it continues to be a substantial and crucial addition to our knowledge and understanding of medications and treatments.

6. References:

- (1) Sarker SD. Pharmacognosy in modern pharmacy curricula.
- (2) Badal S., Delgoda R. Pharmacognosy: Fundamentals, Application and Strategy. Elsevier; 2017.
- (3) Badal S., Byfield G., Brown MC et al. Areas of science embraced by pharmacognosy: constituent sciences of pharmacognosy. In: Badal S., Delgoda R., eds. Pharmacognosy.
- (4) Kamel M. S., History of Pharmacognosy and Herbal Medicine.
- (5) Chester K., Tamboli E., Paliwal S., Ahmad S. Significance of molecular markers in pharmacognosy: a modern tool for authentication of herbal drugs.
- (6) Allard P-M., Bisson J., Azzollini a et al. Pharmacognosy in the digital era: shifting to contextualized metabolomics.

- (7) Bakiri A., Plainchont B., de Paulo Emerenciano V et al. Computer-Aided Dereplication and structure elucidation of natural products at the University of REIMS.
- (8) World Health Organization. Accessed November, 2005.
- (9) Newman DJ., Cragg GM., Snader KM. Natural products as sources of new drugs over the period 1981-2002.
- (10) Witiak DT. Drug Prototypes and their Exploitation by Walter Sneader. John Wiley and Sons Ltd; 1996.
- (11) Dewick PM. Medicinal Natural Products: A Biosynthetic Approach. 2nd ed. John Wiley and Sons; 2002.
- (12) Jones WP. Chin Y-W., Kinghorn AD. The role of pharmacognosy in modern medicine and pharmacy.
- (13) Alamgir ANM. Therapeutic Use of Medicinal Plants and Their Extracts: Volume 1.
- (14) Douglas Kinghorn A., Kinghorn DA. Pharmacognosy in the 21st century
- (15) Kim D-M., Cha E-C., Chung K-J. Pharmacognosy for Korean medical food in the 21st century.
- (16) Nilan TJ., Raveendran R. Marine pharmacognosy.
- (17) Biswas D. Role of reverse pharmacognosy in finding lead molecules from nature.
- (18) Saeidnia S., Gohari AR., Manayi A. Reverse Pharmacognosy and Reverse Pharmacology two closely related approaches for drug discovery development.
- (19) Takenaka T. Classical vs Reverse Pharmacology in Drug Discovery.
- (20) Lee JA., Uhlik MT., Moxham CM. Tomandl D., Sall DJ. Modern phenotypic drug discovery is a viable, Neoclassic Pharma Strategy.
- (21) Swinney DC., Anthony J. How were new medicines discovered?
- (22) Orhan I. E. (2014). Pharmacognosy: Science of natural products in drug discovery.
- (23) Patwardhan B., Chaguturu R. Innovative Approaches in Drug Discovery: Ethnopharmacology, Systems Biology and Holistic Targeting. Elsevier Science; 2016.
- (24) M. Pharm Pharmacognosy, Jobs, Scopes, Salary in India.
<https://www.getmyuni.com/mpfarm-pharmacognosy-jobs-scope->

